

Studies on the Possibility of Using Zinc-EDTA Chelate as a Combined Micronutrient Fertilizer and Soil Iron Mobilizer

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Two alluvial soils of West Bengal were incubated for different lengths of time separately with starch, EDTA and Zn-EDTA, the equilibrium pH values were measured and relative quantities of iron going into the solution phase were determined. Amongst the above reagents only EDTA (di sodium salt) has been found to depress the soil pH to a marked extent. In case of starch or Zn-EDTA, a trend towards increasing the pH was noticed; especially, in the soil characterized by a wider C:N ratio (Harin-soil). The initial rate of mobilization of iron was very high when EDTA was used but the micronutrient element was released at a more or less constant rate throughout the incubation period when Zn-EDTA was employed. Starch is apparently more effective than Zn-EDTA as a soil iron mobilizer in Harin-soil. In the other soil (Rana-soil), however, the following general order of efficiency was observed: EDTA > Zn-EDTA > starch. It has been suggested that Zn-EDTA chelate may be used quite effectively as a combined zinc fertilizer and soil iron mobilizer.

THE form of iron best absorbed by plants appears to be ferrous¹, the availability of which depends in general on the pH and aeration of the soil. Chelating donor groups such as amino, imino, carboxyl, etc. present in degraded soil organic matter like fulvic acid² and small chain organic compounds³ help to dissolve the ferric micelle and encourage its reduction under anaerobic conditions. Immobilization of iron may occur in soil through chemical precipitation as hydrous oxides, phosphates and various inorganic salts or ferric salts of small chain fatty acids⁴, as well as by the influence of iron bacteria⁵.

Wallace and Coworkers⁶ studied the comparative ability of several synthetic chelating agents in mobilizing iron in soil and they discussed the use of metal chelates, particularly those with amino polycarboxylic acids, as a source of micronutrient supply to plants. Natural chelating agents like malic acid⁷ can compete favourably for iron with chelates like Fe-EDTA having stability constants 10^{25} or less.⁸

In the present investigation effects of starch, EDTA and Zn-EDTA on the mobilization of iron in soil have been studied with a view to not only ascertain the relative efficiency of those substances but also to explore the possibility of using Zn-EDTA as a combined soil iron mobilizer.

Materials and Methods

Soils: Two alluvial soil samples (Gangetic alluvium) one from Haringhata and the other from Ranaghat, both of the district Nadia, West Bengal were collected from the upper 0-9" layer of the

respective area. The Haringhata soil (Harin-soil) was procured from a cultivated paddy field which received moderate quantities of N- and P- fertilizers and irrigation water. The Ranaghat soil (Rana-soil) was collected from a mango grove. The soil samples were air-dried, ground and passed through 100-mesh sieve. Important properties of the soils are given in Table I.

TABLE I. IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS UNDER INVESTIGATION

No of Expt.	Properties	Haringhata soil (Harin-soil)	Ranaghat soil (Rana-soil)
1.	Moisture percentage	4.66	4.95
2.	Porespace	47.93%	45.66%
3.	Moisture holding capacity	40.52%	42.94%
4.	Nitrogen (%)	0.11	0.09
5.	Organic carbon (%)	1.01	1.08
6.	Available P-Bray-I (mg/100g soil)	0.54	0.62
7.	Soil pH (1:5 ratio)	6.15	6.30
8.	C.E.C. (me/100 g soil)	10.56	16.04
9.	Total iron (%)	6.57	5.55
10.	Free ferric oxide (%)	2.90	1.62
11.	Exchangeable Fe ^{II} , Fe ^{III} and pH 3.0-soluble iron (mg/100g soil)	1.40	2.94

Reagents: A standard EDTA (disodium salt) solution was prepared and Zn-EDTA solution was obtained by mixing a requisite quantity of EDTA with a known volume of standard zinc solution. Both the solutions were finally diluted to 0.05M and pH adjusted to 7.0 by adding a few drops of dilute HCl or NaOH solution. A 1% starch solution was prepared by the usual procedure.

De-ionized water was used for the above preparations and the solutions stored in polythene bottles. All the reagents were of A.R. quality.

Apparatus: A systronics pH-meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes and a Spectronic-20 (Bausch and Lomb) spectrophotometer were used for the measurements of pH and spectral absorbances respectively.

Method: Iron was determined colorimetrically by the use of *o*-phenanthroline as colour-forming reagent⁹. Combined exchangeable Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and dilute acid soluble iron was estimated by the procedure described by Jackson¹⁰. Free ferric oxide was determined by the dithionite-citrate procedure¹¹.

Experimental

5 G- portions of each soil were taken in 100 ml Corning glass beakers and subjected to the following treatments :

- (a) Soil+10 ml of starch solution+15 ml of de-ionized water;
- (b) Soil+3 ml of EDTA solution+22 ml of de-ionized water;
- (c) Soil+3 ml of Zn-EDTA solution+22 ml of de-ionized water;
- (d) Soil+25 ml of de-ionized water.

Each of the soil samples with above treatments were stirred thoroughly and incubated separately for three different lengths of time, such as 1, 7 and 30 days. One drop of chloroform was added to each beaker with a view to suppress microbial activity in the systems and the beakers were then kept at room temperature under shade. Level of water in each beaker was maintained constant by frequent addition of requisite quantity of water.

TABLE 2. CHANGE OF SOIL pH DUE TO DIFFERENT TREATMENTS

Treatment	Incubation period (Days)	pH*	
		Harin-soil	Rana-soil
Starch	1	6.10	6.30
	7	6.05	6.55
	30	6.30	6.45
EDTA	1	5.75	5.80
	7	5.80	6.00
	30	6.10	6.25
Zn-EDTA	1	6.10	6.30
	7	6.40	6.48
	30	6.22	6.45
Control	1	6.18	6.36
	7	6.26	6.30
	30	5.88	5.95

*Mean of three replications.

After the desired period of incubation, equilibrium pH values of the soil suspensions were determined. These are given in Table 2. The suspensions were then filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter paper

under reduced pressure. No washing of the residue was done. The filtrates were digested with a mixture of concentrated H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ on a hot plate to break the complexed metal ions and to decompose the organic substances. These were evaporated to dryness, brought back into solution by adding 5 ml of concentrated HCl and the iron content was estimated directly from it by the usual *o*-phenanthroline method. The results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3. EFFECT OF DIFFERENT TREATMENTS ON THE RELEASE OF SOIL IRON

Treatment	Incubation period (Days)	Iron* (mg/100 g soil)	
		Harin-soil	Rana-soil
Starch	1	0.84	1.10
	7	7.86	42.50
	30	28.75	68.12
EDTA	1	4.45	10.75
	7	60.10	82.05
	30	94.50	110.10
Zn-EDTA	1	1.15	1.52
	7	18.22	22.86
	30	66.75	65.25
Control	1	0.84	0.98
	7	6.08	16.76
	30	22.00	8.80

*Mean of three replications.

Results and Discussion

Table 2 indicates that when EDTA is used, there is a lowering of soil pH at the initial stage but on prolonged incubation, pH values tend to return to the original level. When Zn-EDTA is employed, no such decrease in pH is observed. This is obviously due to the fact that free and exchangeable metal ions like Fe³⁺, Cu²⁺, etc. present in soil may react instantaneously with EDTA liberating H⁺ ions in the medium, but no such reaction can take place when Zn-EDTA is incorporated. A little increase in observed pH may be due to interaction of hydrous metal oxides with EDTA or Zn-EDTA. The principal reactions may be shown in the following manner :

(where the disodium salt of EDTA is denoted by Na₂H₂Y).

The stability constants of Zn-EDTA (log K = 16.7) and Fe^{III}-EDTA (log K = 25.1) permit the above reactions to occur in soil. With the increase in pH of the medium the reactions (2) and (4), shown above, are greatly inhibited since the increasing hydroxyl ion activity α_{OH}- obviously favours the backward reaction. Due to very low solubility product of ferric hydroxide (—log K_s = 37.4) even the other two reactions (1 and 3) would tend to

proceed sluggishly at higher pH. Thus, in alkaline or highly calcareous soils use of Fe^{III}-EDTA as an instant iron fertilizer has not been proved very successful. Hydroxyl ions, alone or along with the phosphates act as a strong competitor for H₂Y²⁻ ions under such conditions. In mildly acidic soils ferric phosphates (Fe PO₄) may be dissolved by H₂Y²⁻ ions without affecting the pH of the media.

Starch has no immediate effect on soil pH, particularly in Harin-soil, which is originally deficient in organic matter. The increase in pH in Rana-soil upto 7 days of incubation could be explained in the following manner. Due to wider C : N ratio microbial activity was so high in this soil that one drop of chloroform could not suppress it markedly and the added starch, was largely consumed by the microbes. Production of any organic acid was minimum at this stage and the medium was a highly reducing one. On prolonged incubation, however, microbial activity was arrested, possibly due to shortage in nitrogen supply and the acidic degradation products of starch could subsequently lower down the pH of the medium. Increase in soil pH is generally associated with the reduction of some constituents like hydrous oxides of iron, manganese, etc. present on clay colloids.

From Table 3 it is clear that even on simple water-logging (control) iron becomes progressively more and more available with the increase in incubation period. In Rana-soil the increase in soluble iron content is more striking and the rate of mobilization is quite high. Although Harin-soil contains more total iron as well as more free oxides of it, the above observation can be explained in the light of the wider C : N ratio of the Rana-soil. Under the circumstances, reducing environment created in the soil is more intense leading to the formation of more soluble ferrous compounds and on prolonged incubation, greater amounts of soluble ferric chelates are produced with the polydentate organic ligands derived from soil organic matter.

Starch has no immediate effect on the mobilization of iron, obviously because it is not a direct chelating agent. Even after 7 days of incubation, Harin-soil shows only a marginal increase in soluble iron content over the control. Original soil organic matter and distinct microbial activity seem to be responsible for rather exceedingly high rate of iron mobilization in Rana-soil during the early phases of incubation. It is anticipated that most of this soluble iron must be in the ferrous state due to highly reducing environment set up under such conditions. Organic chelating substances subsequently produced should account for further mobilization of the element.

In both the soils EDTA has been found to be the most effective iron mobilizer. Since the Fe-EDTA chelate is essentially anionic in nature, it is less apt to take part in exchange or fixation reactions in soil which, apart from the high stability of the ferric chelate, may also account for high degree of mobilization of iron by EDTA. Even under intense reducing conditions Fe^{III}-EDTA is expected to be the dominant species formed by EDTA since chelates

with other metallic ions such as Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺ and Co²⁺ which are likely to be present in such media are of much lower stability [(log K Fe^{II}-EDTA) = 14.3, log K Mn^{II}-EDTA = 13.8, log K Ca^{II}-EDTA = 16.2]. The rate of iron mobilization by EDTA is very high in both the soils upto 7 days of incubation, after which the rate is diminished to some extent (Fig. 1). An overall higher rate observed for Harin-soil may be ascribed to the higher free oxide content

Fig. 1. Mobilization of iron as a function of time.

from which pool iron is released and subsequently transformed to the labile form as Fe-EDTA. Exchangeable ferrous and ferric ions, hydrous oxide micelle and basic salts of iron with inorganic or organic acids contribute to the initial rate of such transformation. Thus in Rana-soil a higher initial rate of iron mobilization has been observed since this soil is supposed to be richer in the aforesaid constituents.

The availability of iron in both the soils is found to be below in case of Zn-EDTA treatment in comparison to that with EDTA. In Harin-soil relative efficiency of the iron mobilizers, employed in the present investigation, is in the order EDTA > Zn-EDTA > starch, but in case of Rana-soil initial organic matter content evidently contributes to the net availability of iron. With Zn-EDTA the rate of iron mobilization is more or less uniform. The difference in iron availability rates between the EDTA and Zn-EDTA treated soils seems to depend upon the difference in the stability constants of Fe^{III}-EDTA and Zn-EDTA. Amongst the other metal ions present in soil only Cu²⁺ may interfere to some extent in the above ligand exchange reaction [log K_{Cu-EDTA} = 18.8]. Soil texture, pH and forms of iron compounds already present in the soil may also influence the iron availability rates.

Higher pH and wider C : N ratio of the Rana-soil make starch as a more efficient iron mobilizer than

Zn-EDTA. This is not only because of strong reducing condition and microbial activity created by starch in this soil but also because of relatively greater stability of Zn-EDTA in comparison to Fe^{III}-EDTA along with the increase in hydroxyl ion activity. However, iron is released steadily by the interaction of Zn-EDTA with various iron compounds in soil.

Under intensive cultivation programme, it is often advised to use zinc sulphate as a micronutrient fertilizer to combat with various deficiency disorders of field crops. Zinc sulphate has been found to be particularly effective in acid soils and a rather high concentration of Zn²⁺ may be necessary to be present within the plant root zone¹² to have any desired effect. This may, in turn, induce iron deficiency (chlorosis) by interfering with the translocation of the element¹³. The Zn-EDTA chelate may be used as a more versatile micronutrient fertilizer in this respect since plants would absorb it directly just like Fe-EDTA or Fe-EDDHA and loss of efficiency of the element in soil by fixation or ion-antagonism would not arise in this case. Further, the chelate has a better tolerance for higher pH and microbial activity. The higher cost of the compounds may be compensated by the much smaller quantity necessary for the purpose.

Since most soils are well supplied with iron, there is generally no deficiency of this element in soil itself. The present study reveals that under acute conditions of iron immobilization, some soil iron may become mobile by the use of Zn-EDTA while Zn²⁺ produced by the ligand exchange reaction may still remain in soil in the labile pool. Zn-EDTA thus may serve a dual purpose: a potent micronutrient fertilizer and soil iron mobilizer. Further studies on soil-plant relationship involving the use of Zn-EDTA and related chelates are in progress.

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